

Magnetic and Spectral Studies of Complexes of Ni(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) with α -benzilmonoxime*

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Complexes formed by α -benzilmonoxime with Ni(II), Pd(II) and Pt(II) have been synthesised and characterised by elemental analysis, magnetic and spectral studies and the structure of the complexes have been suggested.

STRUCTURAL investigations of tris-complexes of cobalt(III) and rhodium(III) with α -benzilmonoxime (HBMO) have been reported in an earlier communication¹. The present paper describes the preparation, properties and structures of two-colored varieties of Ni(BMO)₂ and Pd(BMO)₂, Pt(BMO)₂ and Ni(BMO)(OAc), where OAc represents an acetate ion.

Experimental

A.R. Grade chemicals and reagents were used. HBMO was prepared by the method reported in the literature². The metal complexes were prepared as indicated below :

Ni(BMO)₂ (red) : 3.5 g of HBMO dissolved in 60 ml of alcohol were added to 50 ml of aqueous solution containing 1 g of nickel sulfate. A red-colored complex was formed at pH 3. The complex was removed, washed thoroughly first with water, then with 0.05N NaOH to remove excess HBMO, if any, and finally with water. It was crystallised from chloroform, dried and analysed. (Required for Ni(BMO)₂-Ni-11.6%, C-66.4%, H-4.0%, and N-5.5%. Found : Ni-11.6%, C-65.8%, H-4.0% and N-5.6%).

Ni(BMO)₂ (green) : To 100 ml of 2% aqueous solution of nickel sulfate, 3 g of ammonium chloride were added. The solution was treated with 3 g of HBMO in 60 ml of alcohol. A green-colored compound separated on raising the pH of the mixture to 8-8.5 with 0.05 M NaOH. It was digested on a water bath for about 10-15 minutes, filtered, washed thoroughly with hot water, recrystallised from chloroform, dried at 110° and analysed. (Required for Ni(BMO)₂ : Ni-11.6%, C-66.4%, H-4.0% and N-5.5%. Found : Ni-11.6%, C-65.8%, H-4.2% and N-5.5%.)

Ni(BMO)(OAc) (Green) : 0.45 g of HBMO in 50 ml of alcohol was added to 50 ml of 1% nickel

acetate solution and the pH of the mixture was raised to 8 by adding 0.1M NaOH solution. A green-colored substance was obtained. It was washed with hot water, recrystallised from chloroform, dried at 110° and analysed. (Required for Ni(BMO)(OAc) : Ni-17.2%, C-55.9%, H-3.8% and N-4.1%. Found : Ni-17.2%, C-55.2%, H-3.8% and N-4.2%).

Pd(BMO)₂ (Green) : 10 ml of 1% solution of palladium chloride in dil.HCl were added to a solution of 0.23 g of HBMO in 30 ml of alcohol. A green-colored compound separated. It was digested on a water bath for about 15 minutes, filtered, washed with water, then with a dilute solution of 1M NaOH and again with water, dried at 110° and analysed. (Required for Pd(BMO)₂ : Pd-19.2%, C-60.6%, H-3.6% and N-5.0%. Found : Pd-19.2%, C-59.7%, H-3.5% and N-5.0%).

Pd(BMO)₂ (red) : The green-colored Pd(BMO)₂ was dissolved in chloroform or benzene and the solvent was removed slowly at room temperature. The process was repeated with the separated solid at least four times when a red-colored compound was obtained. It was kept in a desiccator under vacuum and analysed. (Required for Pd(BMO)₂ (red) : Pd-19.2% C-60.6%, H-3.6% and N-5.0%. Found : Pd-19.2%, C-60.1%, H-3.6% and N-5.1%).

Pt(BMO)₂ (Red) : 3.4 g of HBMO in 50 ml of alcohol were added to 2.5 g of K₂PtCl₆ in 30 ml of water. The mixture was warmed on a water bath for about 15-20 minutes and a red-colored solid was obtained. The solid was separated, washed repeatedly with water, dried at 110° and analysed. (Required for Pt(BMO)₂ : Pt-30.3%, C-52.2%, H-4.3% and N-4.3%. Found : Pt-30.1%, C-51.7%, H-4.5% and N-4.2%).

Instruments used for magnetic and spectral measurements are reported elsewhere^{3,4}.

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The electronic spectra of the complexes in methanol solution show $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the ligand near 40.00kK. Two maxima at 27.77kK ($\epsilon=9,800$) and 24.68kK ($\epsilon=10,280$) and a shoulder at 21.77kK ($\epsilon=1,880$) in the absorption spectrum of the red-colored Ni(BMO)₂ in chloroform may be assigned to metal \rightarrow ligand charge transfer transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1u}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2u}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_g$ in diamagnetic square-planar nickel(II) complexes involving π -bonds⁵.

References

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